

A STUDY OF BULLYING PREVALENCE AMONG SECONDRY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated extent of bullying among secondary school students along with intervention of adults like teachers, parents, elders to prevent bullying and involvement of students in bullying. The researcher also made an attempt to study different forms of bullying and the extent of bullying among boys and girls. Sample selected was 444 students in which 269 boys and 175 girls are included from secondary school students of SSC board from greater Mumbai. Tool used for present study personal data sheet, Olweus bully victim questionnaire were used to collect data. It was found that 17-16 % girls and boys reported that they getting bullied and also reported that they don't have friends. 32% girls and 34 % boys reported that they getting bullied for longer time duration and also found shorter period bullying is more in girls than boys. Surprisingly reporting of bullying to class teacher is shown more by boys than girls.

Key Words : Bullying, Prevalence, OBVQ

INTRODUCTION

School bullying has become a major issue all over the world now a day. Within the education system children are exposed to various cues like attitudes, behavior, and verbal means of socialization. In this process students may tease one another verbally and non-verbally. Sometime few students try to torture other students then it is not a simple teasing but it is to be taken seriously which is called bullying.

It may harm person not only physically but also psychologically. In India, there are many cases of bullying which we got to know from media, they are very worst cases even child loses his/her life sometimes. Therefore there is need to study extent of bullying.

Some definition of bullying given by expert :

Olweus defined that bullying as repeated aggressive bullying acts that are physical, verbal, or indirect in nature and which involve an imbalance of power such that it is difficult for the victim to defend him or herself.

Ross defined as bullying is an intentional and general unprovoked attempt by one or more individuals to inflict physical hurt or psychological distress on one or more victims.

Konstantina defined bullying as the intentional, systematic and unjustified aggressive behavior that is exercised by a student or a group of students, more powerful, physically towards another student or a group of students less powerful.

Operational definition: For the present study, the researcher defined bullying as an aggressive behavior by group of students or an individual through which one tries to suppress weaker students hurting by means of different ways like verbal, nonverbal, physical and emotional bullying.

The review of literature showed that many researches have carried out on bullying such as effect on peer relationship ,academic achievement and behavioral and emotional functioning and nature and extent of bullying ,frequency of bullying behavior ,perception of bullying and effects of anti-bullying policies , bullying behavior and psychological health among school students ,bully victimization among adolescents ,effects on bullying on students' academic performance ,educators intervention in bullying of male and female high school so far studies done in foreign countries .

Very few studies are conducted in India like prevention of school bullying -case study of Coimbatore city, Tamilnadu, study on role of personal family and school factors in school bullying of district Hissar Haryana, as there are few studies found researcher found need to study extent of bullying among boy s and girls of secondary students.

Objectives:

- To study the different forms of bullying.
- To compare different forms of bullying among boys and girls.
- To study the places of bullying.
- To study the extent of bullying in school.
- To compare extent of bullying among boys and girls.
- To study the duration of bullying.

- To study the reaction on bullying by peer.
- To study the fear of bullying among students
- To study the involvement of students in bullying.
- To study the reporting of bullying.
- To study the interventions of adults in bullying.

Method:

Sample : The sample selected for this study comprises of boys and girls studying in class 8th standard of SSC board from greater Mumbai. 444 students were selected among that 269 boys and 175 girls.

Researcher selected variable is only calculating extent of bullying. In the present study researcher adopted descriptive survey method. Descriptive studies are designed to obtain information concerning the current status of phenomenon or about the phenomenon of immediate past. Descriptive studies can explain present condition of education and its students. In that researcher done social survey conducted to know overall social situation of a particular region such as health services available to the public employment opportunities, sanitation problem or it may be social problem like school bullying among children therefor social survey is done to study prevalence of bullying.

Sampling technique: Sampling technique used for present study is a two-stage sampling. At the first stage school from greater Mumbai were selected by random sampling technique, at the second stage students were selected by cluster sampling.

TOOL : 1) Personal Data Sheet
2) Olweus Bully Victim Questionnaire

Analysis of Data : Analysis is done by calculating percentages

Data collected by calculating percentages.

$$\bullet \text{ Percentage} = \frac{\text{No. Of students giving opinion}}{\text{Total number of students}} \times 100$$

For boys and girls percentage was calculated separately for each option.

- For getting gender wise analysis

For boys,

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{No. Of boys giving opinion}}{\text{Total number of boys}} \times 100$$

For girls,
Percentage= $\frac{\text{No. Of girls giving opinion}}{\text{Total number of girls}} \times 100$

5.11 Conclusion and Discussion:

Conclusion and Discussion is divided in to 4 main section to understand in better way.

Section - 1: Friends and general satisfaction with school.

Section - 2: Bullying problems, prevalence, forms of bullying, duration, and reporting.

Section - 3: Feeling and attitudes regarding bullying.

Section - 4: How others react.

Section -1:

The students answered ‘how many good friends do they have in their class ‘ In this it is seen that nearly 17 % girls reported that they don’t have friend or having only one good friend and nearly 16 % boys reported that they don’t have friend or having only one good friend . The results tell us something about overall school climate and students sense of community or connection with school. It is concluded that students having less than two friend in their classes are often bullied.

Students having several good friends may serve as a protective factor against being bullied. Being bullied is also related to disliking school .Very few students reported that they dislike school.

Discussion: The Olweus Sample School Report: Spring 2007, found that 4% of girls and 3% of boys responded that they don’t have any friend or having only one friend, which is very less compared to findings of present study. As it indicate that having one or none friend shows more tendency of being bullied .Compared to foreign country percentage of bullied students is less in Mumbai. This results are contradictory to our findings. The study conducted by Urbansky Conducted study on relationship between school connectedness found that a weak relationship between school connectedness and bully-victimization means when there is bullying school students are not having attachment for school and very weak connectedness towards school, which supports our study co connectedness to school so having less friends as they don’t build healthy relationship with others so having less friends and therefore targeted by others.

Section -2:

Response about being bullied:-

The students answered, How often have you been bullied at school in the past couple of months? To make the results easier the two options combined together i.e. I have not been bullied and only once or twice. Students who chose this option considered to be “not bullied “, in second

category the students who reported “2-3 times a month “,”about once a week “and “several times a week” combined together.

It is seen that nearly 83 % girls reported that they have not been bullied by others and only 16.5 % girls agreed that they getting bullied, and 80 % boys reported that they have not been bullied and only 20 % boys agreed that they getting bullied.

Combining responses alternative this way corresponds to our general definition of bullying which is that the behavior needs to be repetitive compared within boys and girls, it is seen that boys are getting bullied more than girls.

Discussion : Olweus states that the expected level of bullying in a school is about 15 -20 % (Olweus,1993) so this supports finding which researcher got that is 16.5% girls and 20 % boys were bullied . A study done by Wilcox (2005) findings shows that 26 % girls and 30 % boys reported that they were bullied. A study done by Peck L. Showed that 44% girls and 40 % boys were bullied ,this results shows bullying is more in New York than in Mumbai. Results show that many students reported that they have not been bullied by others, it is may be due to that they have fear in their mind about being bullied. it may happen that teasing may be considered as apart of friendship and not as bullying , in other words perception of bullying differ among students. The percentage of students who are bullied is very informative, it is important not to lose sight of the individual student’s .When appraising the prevalence of students being bullied at school the number of girls and boys being bullied are to be considered. A study on prevalence of bullying done by Srisiva in Coimbtore City shows that 56% of students getting bullied by classmates, 37% students being bullied by other students of other class and in total 84 % students reported that they had been subjected to multiple acts of bullying this findings are contradictory to our study which shows results that nearly 20 % students being bullied.

Duration of bullying:

When the students answered about the duration of bullying ,the response alternative for the two highest categories “ about a year “and “several year “have been combined in to one category . It is found that for longer time nearly 32 percentage of girls being bullied and nearly 34 percentage of boys being bullied. The findings indicates that the duration of bullying among boys is more than girls, for longer time and this is serious problem. The findings also show that for a short period bullying among girls it is found nearly 66 percentages and among boys it is nearly 62 percentages. It can be concluded that for short period of time bulling is more in girls than boys.

The students who have been bullied for a long time, clearly indicates the need to initiate or strengthen bullying prevention efforts.

The findings also show that for short time period, bullying among girls is more than boys.

Discussion: It is found that nearly 33% of students reported that bullying has lasted for several years. Among that 33% girls and 34% boys have reported the bullying for longer duration. This finding is supported by Wilcox C. (2005) which shows that nearly 32.4% students reported bullying has lasted for several years

Afraid of being bullied:-

Students answered to the question, How often they afraid of bullying , The finding shows that nearly 22 % girls and 19 % boys are being afraid of being bullied than boys , but the difference between girls and boys afraid of being bullied is considerably fewer .

Discussion : A study of Peck L.(2013) shows that 42% girls and 42% boys were afraid of bullying, these results are nearly double than findings of present study .It shows feeling of being bullied is more in students of New York than students of Mumbai . When there is little difference between girls and boys with regard to actually being bullied such results may reflect the greater vulnerability of girls and /or the reluctance of boys to admit to feelings of insecurity and fear. If students are afraid of being bullied, it very likely will impact their ability to concentrate on learning and cause them not to come to school and to dislike the school environment.

Reporting of bullying:-

Students when answered the question, have bullied students reported to anyone about their experiences? If so, whom?

The findings show that 33 % boys reported to class teacher about (being bullying or) experiences of bullying and 23 % of girls reported to teacher about experiences of bullying .This shows reporting of bullying to class teacher is shown more by boys than girls . 19 % girls reported to their parents about experiences of bullying and only 9 % of boys told to their parents about experiences of bullying .This shows girls reporting of bullying to their parents is more than boys. It shows that 37. 5 girls told their friends and 33 % boys told their friends here also girls told their friends more about bullying experiences than boys.

Discussion: Findings shows that 33% boys and 23% girls reported to teacher about being bullied. A study of Peck L (2013) shows that 18% boys and 20% Girls reported to their class teacher about bullying. The present study shows that boys are reporting more than girls but Peck L found that more girls are reporting than boys.

In present study the percentage of students told friends about being bullied are 33% boys and 37% girls. A study done by Peck L (2013) shows that 25.9% boys and 68.6% girls told to their friends about being bullied. It shows more number of girls told their friends than boys which is

supporting our findings. In present study 19% girls and 9% boys told to their parents and the study by Peck L (2013) shows that 62.9% girls and 37% boys told to their parents. This is contradictory to findings of our study but it shows high awareness about reporting of bullying in students of foreign countries than students in Mumbai.

A study done by Croucier R. on teachers perceptions of bullying at the elementary school level found teachers responded bullying rarely occurred in classroom this findings support to our study as in our study nearly 32% percent students reported to teachers about being bullied ,this also shows that unless and until students don't report to teachers they con not get aware of bullying happened in class .They will only say that there is less bullying happening in the class.

Ways of bullying: -

The various forms of bullying ,experienced by students who are bullied .The results were taken of girls and boys have been verbally bullied 2- 3 times a month or more often . Verbal bullying is usually the most prevalent form for both boys and girls. Negative comments is almost always an inherent characteristics of bullying. It is seen that nearly 33 % boys and 28 % girls being verbally bullied.

21 % girls reported that left out of things purposely, excluded from group experienced this percentages is more than boys, only 16 % boys reported that they were left out of things and excluded from groups.

In case of money or things taken away or damaged that type of bullying shown by 17 % boys which is more than girls. 14 % girls shows such type of bullying.

Results analyses the possible gender difference which have been examined by taking in to account who is bullied by whom. This help to ascertain what forms of bullying are used by each gender.

It is seen that 38 % girls being bullied from both boys and girls and 33 % boys being bullied from both boys and girls , means the percentages of girls is more of getting bullied by both boys and girls ,also it is seen that boy to boy bullying is more than girl to girl .

Bullying in same class is more than the bullying in different grades. When girl bully girl they tend to use more subtle and indirect forms, including social isolation and spreading of rumors. However, these forms of bullying are also used by many boys towards both girls and boys. Bullying by physical means is a special characteristic of boys in particular relation to other boys but also in

relation to girls.

Discussion: in case of Wilcox (2005) 33.3% girls and 29% boys experienced verbal bullying which is supporting to findings of present study, which shows 33% boys and 28% girls experienced verbal bullying. The study done by Peck L shows 9.1% girls and 9.1% boys experienced verbal bullying, which is contradictory to our study.

Excluded from group: in case of Wilcox (2005) 33% girls and 17.8% boys reported that they were excluded from group. Present study findings shows that 21% girls and 16% boys reported that they were excluded from groups. Which shows girls reported more exclusion from group.

Hit, kicked, pushed, shoved or locked indoors: in case of Wilcox (2005) which shows that 11% girls and 16% boys reported hitting, kicking, pushing and locking indoors, while present study shows that 11% girls and 14% boys reported such incidence which is supporting to our studies.

A study done by Matsuda T. (2000) conducted study on Bullying among children and adolescents ,they found that 77% students experienced verbal bullying which is contradictory to our study ,in our study nearly 31% students reported verbal bullying .

Where bullying occurs: -

The results of question concerning the places where the bullying has occurred.

Findings shows that bullying happened in class is more when teacher is not present in class. It is seen that 9% bullying happened when teacher is present in class and 34% bullying happened when teacher is not present in class, which is high. This should certainly be a matter of concern for the teaching staff .It is also useful to compare the level of bullying occurring in the classroom when the teacher is and is not present.

It is found that 21.4 % girls getting bullied on playground /athletic field which is more than boys, nearly 17 % boys getting bullied on playground.

Girls getting bullied in gym class is more than boys. In lunch room 8 % boys getting bullied. 21% boys getting bullied somewhere in school which is more than girls.

Discussion: In case of Wilcox (2005), bullying occurred on playground the finding shows that 76 % girls and 57% boys reported that bullying occurs on playground. In present study 21% girls and 17 boys reported that bullying on playground, which is less compared to Wilcox study. The study of Peck L. shows bullying occurred on playground 16.7% girls and 16.3% boys reported which supports present study.

Bullying occurs when class teacher is not present in class in that case present study shows that 36.4% girls and 29.7% boys reported being bullied. In case of Wilcox study findings shows that

53.8% girls and 32.4% boys reported about being bullied. In case of Peck L study shows that 38.5% girls and 29.1% boys reported about being bullied this shows Peck L study findings support to the present study. A study conducted by Stuchell J.(2007) on teachers and students perspectives on the characteristics of bullying found that most bullying occurred in the hallways/ staircase which is contradictory to our study that only 0.74 % boys and 2.86 % girls reported bullying occurs in hallways / staircase ,so only nearly 1.58 % students reported bullying in that area .A study done by Connor and Graber (2014) reported that incidents of bullying were more likely to occur during physical education and they discovered that most incidents of bullying takes place in locker rooms where students dress and get ready for P.E. which contradictory to our study which found that nearly 20 % students reported bullying on playground and gym class. More bullying happened when class teacher is not present in class than on play ground .

Section – 3:

Feeling and attitudes regarding bullying:

Joining in bullying: Findings shows that nearly 23 % girls reported that they could join in bullying a student whom they do not like and 22 % boys reported that they could join bullying to whom they don't like, this shows more percentage of girls agreed they will join in bullying .39 % girls denied that they could join in bullying and 34 % boys denied that they could join in bullying.

Discussion: study of Wilcox (2005) shows that nearly 72 % students reported that they would not join in bullying to other students and this findings supports to our study nearly 70 % students reported that they would not join in bullying to other students.

Empathy for others:

Findings shows the percentages of students who say they “feel a bit sorry “ or “feel sorry and want to help “ are the student showing empathy towards students who getting bullied . Findings shows that 72 % girls and 71% boys showing empathy towards other students who getting bullied. Only nearly 10 % girls reported they don't feel much and 13 % boys reported they don't feel much. 17 % girls reported that probably they deserves for that and 15 % boys reported that they deserve for that .But more percentage of girls and boys having empathy for students can be turned in to actions that will help the bullied students .

Discussion: A study done by Wilcox C (2005) shows that 66.6% students responded that they feel sorry and want to help while the present study findings shows that nearly 63% students feel a sorry and want to help which is supporting to our study , which shows nearly 72 % students showing empathy towards other students who getting bullied.

It is important to emphasize ,however ,that the reported level of empathy with students who are

being bullied are generally quite high may be students thought that it may happen to them also .

Section - 4:

How others react:

Some questions like question number 20 ,21 and 39 are designed to capture the perceptions of all students .Other question concern the perceptions of students who are bullied (Q 22) or students who bully other student (Q 34 and 35) . Q 37 also reflects the student's view of their own reaction (attitudes/behavior) towards a bullying situation.

Intervention of teachers /other adults and peers:

The findings show that when girls are getting bullied ,teachers show s more concern to girls than boys ,for example 24 % teachers intervene to stop bullying when girls getting bullied and 19 % teachers intervene to stop bullying when boys getting bullied .

13 % adults at home intervene to stop bullying when girls getting bullied and 10 % adults at home intervene to stop bullying when boys getting bullied.

In general (Q 20) teachers or other adults at school or other students who “try to put a stop to bullying when a student is being bullied at school ,in this it is seen that adults at school try to put a stop to it when girls bullied at school .

It is seen that nearly 50 % other students try to put stop at bullying when boys are getting bullied and nearly 47 % other student try to put a stop when girls are getting bullied , from this result it is seen that other student try to stop bullying than adults at school .

It is seen that adults at home contacted the school to try to stop bullying in this it is find out that 28 % girls and nearly 25 % boys reported that no one at home contacted to school to try to stop bullying. Only 5 % girls reported that many time adults at home contacted to school and 8 % boys reported that adults at home contacted several time. This shows adults are not taking the bullying seriously only 5-8 % parents contacted school to stop bullying.

Discussion: Olweus Sample School Report :Spring 2007 reported that nearly 60 % teacher intervene to stop bullying when girls getting bullied and nearly 50 % teachers intervene when boys getting bullied .This findings supports our findings that more number of teachers intervene when girls are getting bullied. Also the report of Olweus shows that 52% adults at home intervene to stop bullying when girls are getting bullied, and 41% adults at home intervene when boys are getting bullied .This shows more number of adults at home intervene compared to our study which

contradicts to our findings. Olweus study also shows nearly 33 % other students try to stop bullying when girls are getting bullied and 27% other students try to stop bullying when boys are getting bullied. This results also contradictory to our study where 50 % other students intervene when girls getting bullied and 47% other students intervene when boys getting bullied. Bucy A.(2010) conducted study on educators interventions in bullying of male and female high school students in Ohio ,shows that female teachers choosing a higher level of intervention for male victims than did male teachers and male teachers chose a higher level of intervention for female victims than male victims.

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